

LOIS LANE'S ENIGMATIC ARTICLE: WHY DOESN'T THE WORLD NEED SUPERMAN?!

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ABSTRACT

This article takes a psychoanalytic approach to Lois Lane's article about Superman's disappearance, five years after the incident, in which, after being reluctant to write it, she does so, but not before delving into a deep reflection on her life and her career alongside the most powerful Super Hero in the Universe. All her memories are marked by the few moments they were together, trying to hide that the professional she had become in the local and international journalistic scene was not entirely due to Azulão but rather to her friend and editorial colleague, for her infantilized, Clark Kent. The article reveals itself, in the end, to be an enigma, which she herself cannot decipher, since she ended up closed in a domestic life, in which there was nothing or no one to compete with and, the idea of thinking that, one day, Superman would return and, together with his best competitor, Clark could make all the longing for the freedom he once experienced return to lash his rebellious spirit, now tamed, a fortiori. Lois's work induces the reader to think of Kal as an idol; However, public and critical interpretation takes it as having a motivating bias and she ends up winning the Oscar for journalism. This is another blow to her ego, because she expected to be punished for destroying the immaculate image that Superman had built as a god and that, in a cowardly way, left her in longing and loneliness, taking her best friend with her, which made she abandons her a successful career to become a devoted wife and mother. Her hatred was not at the loss of love and friend; but, what she had become, because of Superman's abandonment.

Keywords: Lois Lane. Clark Kent. Super man. DailyPlanet.

INTRODUCTION

When news broke that scientists had discovered traces in the galactic zone where Planet Krypton, Kal L's homeland, was supposedly located, reporter Clark Kent sets out in search of answers, driven by an empty and obscure hope that he could find any remaining traces of their homeland. For a long five years, Superman remains missing from the skies of Metropolis, to the despair of two people who were unable to deal with his disappearance and took this event

as abandonment: the Daily Planet reporter Lois Lane and the bald billionaire sacripant, Lex Luthor.

Lois Lane goes into despair over the disappearance of the Champion of Metropolis and reports, later, in her memoirs, that at first, it was a wait that then evolved into a vigil and he did not appear, nor did he respond to her calls. Along with him, his great friend and writing and journalistic research colleague, Clark Kent, who, over the years had silently become her great inspiration for becoming a highly respected reporter around the world, also disappears. , mainly because of its revealing and bold reports that helped reveal major crimes in all areas.

Five years after the Man of Steel's disappearance, Perry White, editor of the Daily Planet, commissions Lois to write an article in the form of a plea so that, in some semblance of hope, the Hero reads it and returns to his home, Metropolis. The proposed title was "Because the world needs Superman" and the simple idea of having to think of something to talk about her former platonic love displaces her, leaving her plunged into a personal hell, seeking to understand the reasons why led them to leave, abandoning everyone, especially her. In the end, as a way of coming to peace with herself, she takes the blame for his disappearance, believing that she had put herself at risk too many times in the expectation that he would appear and save her.

He writes the infamous article after struggling for sleepless nights on end, and the title is the opposite of what Perry had asked him to do; However, it ends up enchanting the editor and the public and specialized critics award it the *Oscar* for journalism. As much as one might think it was a mistake or a gesture of revenge, he wasn't saying anything false. The one he missed, in fact, wasn't Superman, it was his friend and colleague in investigative adventures, whom he mocked and infantilized at all times; not because she didn't like him or because she considered him inferior to her; simply because I admired him and hated having to admit it.

Lois' article turns out to be a true enigma that she herself was unable to decipher. Lost between anger and passion, unable to return to being the investigative reporter she once was, because of the consequences of her choices, she enters a new cycle of conflict, accusing Superman of being responsible, once again, for your misfortune. Even with the return of her old co-worker, nothing could be as it was before, because there was a marriage that prevented her and forced her to live a normal life, like most other women in the world.

This all makes her accuse Kal of throwing her life into the most complete and insoluble chaos. The worst thing in the life of a human being is comparison and every time Lois tried to evaluate her wonderful life now with her life full of risks in the past, the longing for the

adventure turned the memory into an insane act of pain and anger, in which the culprit was Superman, for having abandoned her, who knows why.

This was the oracle of your article, the future is always more objective, as long as you never compare it with the past. In her gift there were Jason and Richard. But, in his history there was Clark and Superman. These two made her a journalism legend; the first two made her a suburban housewife, mother and wife. If she understands the message to be deciphered, imprinted in her work, she would never look back on her glorious days and think about the present.

LOIS LANE'S ENIGMASTIC ARTICLE

Lois Lane, the brilliant reporter for the Daily Planet, always at the side of her great country friend and who, over time, transformed him into her protege Clark Kent, became the closest figure to Superman, so much so that they fell in love . But even Lois's love for Kal is a strange response to an expression of value she gave him, always sure of himself, without being arrogant, like his arch-rival Lex Luthor was.

However, what we intend to analyze here is why the article he writes in the newspaper that has always praised the Man of Steel must be taken as an element marked and carried by a complex enigma that proves difficult to decipher. The original title of the text is: *Why doesn't the world need Superman?* , stating such a thing; however, the doubts and the feeling of devastation that affect her lead her to question whether the title of her text should not be followed by an exclamation mark or question mark; exactly, the unconscious reading that your reader was driven to create in his thoughts, *quid-pro-quo* !

So, what actually won him the *Pulitzer Prize* for journalism that year, it was the title of his article and not it itself, which became more of an adornment. Throughout the lines he lets all his resentment against the Hero's abandonment dominate his creative and philosophical spirit and explains that, in the Champion's absence, the individuals of Metropolis learned to live without him, in the same way as it was before his existence. This demonstrates empirical proof of resilience the likes of which humans have never experienced before in history.

The question about resilience, incorporated by Psychology into the common sense of all *coaches*, is an element that requires a very complex hermeneutic to be applied to it and that clarifies the meaning of the situation itself and not just the term, as if it , in itself, could determine a state of absolute overcoming and individual behavior as if nothing stood between man and his desire to win the battles that are put before him on a daily basis. The word was

borrowed from Physics and is used to test the resistance of steel in industries. The steel sheet is subjected to intense pressure and then measures how much it was able to return to its original state (before being subjected to the test). It turns out that, no matter how sensitive depression is, it does not cease to exist and, with human beings, the same thing happens, because there is a situation that affects them called epigenetics, in which once having gone through a crisis, overcoming is never such that it leaves no trace of consequences, given that man is a being who seeks to adapt to situations so that he can face them on future occasions, if necessary. Human resilience is a skill that is developed based on the individual's ability to find solutions to become flexible and adapt to situations that are beyond their control. It's not about always getting out of a critical situation unscathed; It is about developing the ability to deal with the crisis efficiently and emerge from it stronger.

While everyone was able to read her article and interpret the message she was sending them, she was unable to deal with the guilt that was ravaging her that she was blaming Kal for all her sadness who, at the same time he left he had taken with him his great friend and pupil, Clark. I could even understand that I would miss Superman, a lot perhaps...; But why did I feel so sad about the loss of the clumsy Hillbilly in the chicken pants?

I would never make the connection that they were both one person; in her [*always*] confused head, Clark had abandoned her, simply because he had dared to destroy the immaculate [*until then*] image of his Champion and, Perry White tried to reassure her by saying that it wasn't his article that sent the Man of Steel away , especially because it was written after his departure. Could it be that the editor of Planeta Diário was referring to his reporter Clark Kent, in a condition of unconscious analysis, a flawed act expressed from the hermeneutic reading of the deafening silence that reigned in the newsroom regarding the young man's disappearance, without any explanation?

The article, in itself, is already an enigma because it was written by someone who loved Superman more than anything else and who lived depending on him to save his life from countless dangers that he put himself through recklessness and the trust he placed in the Hero. . Applying a deep analysis metric, we have that the expression *world*, in the title, can be replaced by *I* and from then on you have the first confusion of languages, in which your Ego expressed something, tremendously confusing, and your Superego tried to correct it in the way it understood it could and, if there was no judgment about it, it was because the same confused egoic reading that affected her in the production of the work also affected her readers and the judges who judged it.

It's not about having learned to live and overcome the hardships of life in the absence of the Champion of Metropolises; It's about learning to overcome the dependence that humans have on their idols. Just like Nietzsche, Lois called into question everyone's faith in an idol, casting a terrible twilight over it. However, how commendable should this prove to be? Was what he had written about human resilience, without Superman, actually true? Did humans become stronger, wiser, more self-assured after his departure? When you destroy an idol, what will you offer in its place? Will everyone become their own idol? Superman confronts her in this regard and Lois ends up immersed in the deepest silence that the abyss could return to her through her gaze.

This is the neuralgic point that never ceased to devastate the reporter's thoughts, because she herself was putting herself in danger, not because she was counting on the triumphant arrival of her protector to save her; It was the courage he always showed that infected her and pushed her to go further. Superman is a signifier and what he means, to everyone, even his most ardent enemies, is what makes him so special.

But what makes Lois's article such an enigma? An enigma means something that is difficult to understand, difficult to define or know in depth, and that is characterized by being ambiguous or metaphorical. It is related to the unknown; therefore, it needs to be interpreted first and then deciphered. In the case of the object of study in question, which we are now focusing on, in the title, translated into Portuguese, there is a detail that may cast doubt on what the author wanted to reveal or demonstrate with her text: The coordinating conjunction *because* it has variations specific grammatical features that, when expressed in Portuguese, infer particular meanings to the period. When expressed at the beginning of interrogative sentences, it must be written separately, so that the reader understands that it is a question. When at the beginning of an explanatory sentence, it must be spelled together, so that the reader's brain understands the period as an explanatory process. In the case of the phrase that stands as the title of the aforementioned article, despite presenting itself as a question, the conjunction actually comes together at the beginning of the sentence. Of course, in the world of comics and Literature, the poetic license that authors take with complete freedom allows them to create antagonisms and other situations that are subject to punishment outside the world of fantasy.

But this is not the case with Lois' article, in which she wants to provoke the reader into a deep reflection on who Superman is to the world, what he effectively represents for each person; what is its importance in this world, since wars continue to happen, hunger, disasters, violence, deaths and someone with your power does not interfere in order to put an end to all of this.

The way it was written induced the brain to read it, at first, as a question and, obviously, there would be the expectation that the answer would be revealed in the text. However, the confusion caused would force a second reading, which would not go beyond the title, because it was an enigma, not the text, which was incapable of revealing the truth and resolving the confusion that had arisen. Lois, in her unrestrained anger at the abandonment of her two loves, tries to make everyone hate Superman, inducing the idea that he had become an idol, when, what had actually happened is that he had become a symbol of hope, not one's own. When the citizens of Metropolis looked up at the sky and saw that blue and red spot flying over the buildings, it didn't mean that their problems would cease to exist, just that there was hope, despite everything.

Since very primitive times, man has always raised his gaze to the sky in search of a sign that could give him expectations regarding his endeavors. He never did it in search of the condition that the gods would do what was due to him, but rather in search of a sign that his protective god was there, in some unknown place, intervening for him and this made him feel safe in their undertakings. This is a phylogenetically inherited behavior. It was the priests of Antiquity who transformed the gods into idols, because that way they could control everyone's feelings.

Since Nietzsche announced that God was dead, it had been a long time since anthropocentrism had made man no longer look to the heavens in search of his protector, so that he could be filled with hope in the face of some sign. They have been under the shadow of evil imposed by Catholic priests for so long that they have forgotten the existence of God. The DC Comics writers were clever in taking advantage of this intrinsic human condition of searching the skies for some sign of hope and created a character who lived flying over the skies of the city of Metropolis, dressed in colors that stand out in the sunlight.

Lois' article tended to lead everyone to believe that Kal had become an idol and, as a result, humans lost their courage and determination to solve their own problems. However, that was not how they received and interpreted him, because even though 5 (five) long years had passed without his figure being seen in the city's skies, no one had lost hope and faith in the Champion of Metropolis. Even the critic that won the *Pulitzer* interprets the text as a call to maintain expectations in its hero.

Kal never took for himself the image of a god or an idol; He remained a calm and concerned figure with all life on the Planet and, if he did not get involved in geopolitical conflicts, it was for reasons of ethics and respect for each nation and the sovereignty that belongs to each of them. He learned well that, as the most powerful creature on Earth, whichever

side he took in a war meant the defeat and imminent end of the other. History had already taught about this, so what could be done was to fight alongside the competent bodies for the maintenance and restoration of peace between peoples.

When Lois understands that her article was a revenge against Superman, in which she wanted all the hatred she felt against him to be shared by everyone, she feels conflicted, exactly, because this may have taken away from her the person who gave the most meaning to her life. your existence, Clark. What had led her partner to disappear, to abandon her, as Superman had done? Not giving you news? How would you be? Where would it be? The article's enigma cannot be resolved; even for Lois, when she takes it in a deeper and less heated reading, with a wide distance from the object feeling that produced it, she finds herself facing an oracle. Therefore, he claims that Superman is always throwing her into chaos!

WHO DOES LOIS MISS: CLARK KENT OR KAL L?

Lois Lane's relationship with her two loves is a comic book phenomenon that television and cinema managed to capture very well, building a love triangle for myopic eyes. It turns out that, if there is one thing that never existed on the part of the award-winning reporter, it was love, towards either of them, Clark and Superman; This is because her psychology is an amalgam that requires an accurate interpretation.

Lois saw in Clark an opportunity to reveal herself as a mother, the one who protects her defenseless son, to whom she needs to provide care, not so special, but without which, a tragedy at home could happen. In relation to Superman, she saw herself in the condition of being understood as the woman who wants to be loved to such an extent by her love, that he always appears to help her in the most difficult moments; in other words, with the presence of both, the representation of the conflict between the woman and the mother could be experienced without it being either of them.

The paradox that arises is that, to be recognized as someone important to Kal, she needed to show herself to be fearless, daring to the extreme and willing to do anything so that she could cross the limit where only he could save her. Over time, the bandits realized that Miss Lane's presence could represent a unique opportunity to see the Champion of Metropolis in the flesh, going beyond an urban legend and a red dot in the sky. This causes the value of bets to rise in the underworld, causing a very experienced [*and jealous*] player to protect his life, Lex Luthor.

In this scenario, Clark becomes nothing more than an idiotic co-worker of Miss Lane, in which his company could mean a way of transferring all his insecurity; In other words,

everything she fought against was reflected in the boy, without having to fight any type of internal conflict, acting as if she were the most powerful and determined woman in the world. Paradoxically, it was this fellow hillbilly and idiot, with his chicken trousers and bowler hat who gave meaning to his life; exactly, because he was a real figure, who was at his side, within reach of his vision, while Superman was a surreal figure, who no one knew exactly where he was and who, luckily, appeared whenever he was in danger; But, there would come a day when she would not hear her pleas and she would have to find a way to free herself from the danger in which she herself had placed herself.

In Lois' psychopathic understanding, Superman had turned into an idol; in a type of god to whom one turned in times of trouble, begging for his help without being able to harbor any kind of hope, and it is because of this feeling towards him that he produced his award-winning article. However, here is a question that defies logic: if Superman was so adored and loved by everyone, why did his article win the Oscar for journalism, instead of being rejected by public opinion and specialized critics? The answer is an understanding of the social feeling that man needs to free himself from his idols; in other words, Azulão was taken as a symbol so that everyone could understand, categorically, the meaning of life and the demands imposed by human existence. His article ends up being awarded for bringing social psychology back into the realm of public discussion. There may be someone who rebelled against his text and, even declaring that it represented a tremendous stab in the back, to clarify who and where it came from; However, all of this is always seen as a *marketing ploy* by every newspaper that intends to survive on its product. The problem was with Lois herself, who could not distinguish between her ideal ego and her pathological ego, necessitating the existence of an idol who adored her and not the other way around. In the end, his article was full of hurt and spite.

But, in an attempt to answer the enigma proposed in the epigraph of this topic, the answer that may seem obvious is not; because the individual Lois misses in her life is young Clark. And the understanding is the simplest one can have: it was with him that she could go out and have lunch; go to a social event, talk about trivial things, such as debts, health, money, employment, compete on equal terms in your professional field, fight with him whenever you want. He was a human, a simple human, someone who went unnoticed among the masses; without understanding, Kent provided him with a type of happiness that Superman could never provide him. However, in an unconscious way, I knew this very well.

When Superman reappears in Metropolis and, at the same time, Clark reappears on the scene, his anger, when he says that the Man-of-Steel throws his world into chaos is due to the fact that he brought his adventure companion back who, At this point, he could no longer

occupy the same space in his world, because, now, there was his biological son who had appeared with the mission of replacing him in the motherhood process that he found himself immersed in, in a psychopathological way.

But what had actually changed in his life in the five years since Superman was away? This is a strange question, because it all seemed too obvious, that Lois had matured, psychologically, as a woman and had gotten married, had a son. However, none of this was enough to soothe the pain of the wound caused by having been abandoned by him. She herself admits that she put herself in danger countless times because she was sure he would come and save her. This was a conscious idea, a mask used to hide that he had done it so many times, for two reasons that he would never dare admit: the first that he needed an excuse to be in his arms; it was a cozy and delightful place to be; secondly because the image of Lois in the Champion's arms took over the world and made her seen as the most envied woman in the world. All his narcissism was expressed there, with the aggravating factor that, over time, it turned into a highly addictive drug, in which the desire to take it became stronger until it became obsessiveness. Behold, he collapses when he finds himself without him, and what's more, everyone understood that, in fact, he had abandoned everyone, from the solitude in which Lois found herself, because everyone asked her where he was, as if she were its owner or the person with sufficient powers to control its presence.

It was from an imperfect self-analysis that he came to the conclusion that the world did not need Superman; that “dealing with loss is one of the most unpleasant aspects of the human condition. The idea that never again seeing someone we depend on, someone we admire, someone we love, hurts. But our ability to grow, to recover, to continue living, crushes the pain. We are a malleable species, and no matter the size of the tragedy, we can pick ourselves up and get back on our feet. All we need is faith in ourselves!” (LOIS LANE, 2006, pp. 24-25).

When you take this quoted part of your article and subject it to rigorous analysis, you come to understand that Lois considers Kal's disappearance as an immeasurable loss, which everyone suffered in their own ways; but, there was no one who did not take it as an unpleasant cup. It reveals that everyone depended on him, in some way, to continue to have hope, whether it was to save them from some phenomenon that could not be dealt with. He says that everyone, without exception, admired him and that, to the same extent, they loved him and it was for this reason that the pain became deeper, more intense, more filled with anger.

It also considers Kal's abandonment as a tragedy that could not be described in terms of its size and even so, everyone could rise again, especially because there was no other way, life and existence were ahead, demanding that they continue and that they learn to live without their

idol. As Batman said, it was necessary for everyone to deprive themselves of the hope that he would return, so that they could continue their lives making plans and relying on what they had. To do this, they would have to transmute the faith they placed in the Kryptonian into themselves.

Returning to the epigraphic question that opens this topic, Lois Lane misses her friend Clark and not Superman. It may seem strange; However, it was thanks to her colleague's company that she became an investigative reporter of high potential, precisely because he was her rival, although he tried not to show any rivalry with her. Lane realized that *Smallville*'s hillbilly was a spectacular, daring, talented investigative reporter and that, beneath that appearance of a shy individual, a powerful lion was hiding and, in order not to be surpassed by him, she needed to go much further, which made her dive headlong into reports that turned into extremely dangerous adventures and, if it weren't for Superman, he would have died in the first of them. So, it wasn't because of the Man of Steel that he took so many risks in his career; It was because of her friend who, although they were the same *persona*, for her, Clark was a powerful enemy who she couldn't let overcome her; For this reason, he always infantilized him, treating him like a clumsy country bumpkin, when in fact he had a respect and admiration for him that bordered on envy.

Apparently, when Superman disappears, all the fire and passion that burned within him also, according to the investigative report, disappears, which could lead to the deduction that, if he risked himself in a dangerous situation, he would no longer come to save him. No mistake, it was the [*silent*] rivalry with her editorial colleague that stoked her investigative ego and made her the best journalist in Metropolis, perhaps in the world.

Clark, behind and through his candid way of motivating people, ended up persuading Perry to let them go in search of answers, even when everything seemed like an insane adventure without any possibility of success. There was something mysterious about him that made it possible to believe that the venture would be productive, and everyone believed that Azulão appeared because of his emotional bond with Lois; but, it was strange that he should appear where Kent was also; mere chance, since they were both work partners and were investigating something together.

The strangest thing was that Lane's voracity and proactivity in relation to her work alienated everyone from her; which didn't happen with Clark who, in a way, felt attracted to her and longed for her company. When Lois senses that she is facing a worthy rival, she adopts him as her own, in the certainty that a dangerous opponent must be kept close and, he was extremely dangerous because he was an unknown quantity; it could not be understood through a hasty

reading and even after years of living with the young man it still remains a mystery to him. This both enchanted and intrigued her and the more she felt challenged to overcome someone she couldn't be. All this effort to overcome Clark had made her a journalism legend and, when she found herself without her most valuable opponent, everything lost its meaning, allowing her to dedicate herself to a domestic life.

When she asks if Superman left because he was tired of saving her life and, of course, she was the one to blame, after all, she didn't need any of that to prove herself as a great reporter; which already makes it clear that, in some way, he came to occupy an empty space in his spirit, not filled in childhood. However, what is clear is that he is thinking about Clark and he cannot hate him for that; despite knowing I could live without Kal; but, what his life became showed that it did not exist without Clark Joseph Kent. It wasn't Superman who motivated her to work and make the most unusual discoveries; journalistic investigation was what made his world a wonderful place and one he liked to live in; but, he needed a stimulus, a challenge that could not be overcome, because he was neurotic and Mr. Smallville managed this feat, even if he did not wish to be treated as a rival to her. Lois never felt anything for Clark other than a volcanic passion for what he represented to her: *an insurmountable adversary* and she kept this image built in her head as long as they were together.

CONCLUSION

Lois Lane and her relationship with Clark and Kal L do not express, as some hasty interpreters wish to understand, a love triangle, because there is no feeling of libidinous desire that can be explored in the psychic construct of any of them. Superman was created to be a superhero everyone could trust with their lives, and masterfully, that's what Lois proved to everyone for decades.

Creating a warrior is a complex task and, if he is left to his own greatness, without having a point of fixation to represent any weakness, he ends up getting lost in his own adventures and, in a short time, the public leaves to feel attracted to him. Lane has been following the Champion since his emergence on the Metropolis scene and his psychology has transformed the existential scene for both Clark and Kal L.

Lois Lane became an emblematic figure in comics and, in particular, in Superman stories, always providing an interesting counterpoint, showing herself as a fragile figure, although this was an amalgam, because her courage made everyone not only admire her as well

as fear; However, there were situations where only Kal's capabilities could save her from the risk of death.

Alongside Clark and Superman, she can express all her madness, transforming her traumas into great achievements, inspiring other women to overcome challenges that, until that moment, were only for men, due to the imminent risks in the process. As time passes and, in an attempt to adjust the characters and stories to the dictates of society, the platonic passion between Lois and Superman evolves into the revelation of their secret identity and into a loving relationship that culminates in marriage. With this transformation, much of the magic was lost and, when analyzing the films and stories, it is when we see the tension produced by the conflict between the desire to reveal the identity and Lane's childhood pressure to know if Clark was the Superman who the stories made more sense to the reader.

As regards the article, which she presented to the newspaper's edition, it was not a disaffection towards Azulão and was directed much more towards Clark Kent, although he did not represent a loss for the world [exactly, *because, for everyone, he was just a reporter for a small North American newspaper*]; but, for Lois, he was the friend she insisted on preserving due to his never manifested potential and this mysterious condition made her go far beyond what she could even imagine in her career.

Even if Clark one day returned to the Daily Planet, things had changed in such a way that all that passionate and violent inspiration that struck her in days gone by could no longer occur, because of the choices she had made when she found herself without her possessions. psychological challenges; because that was how he interpreted their presence in his life. Finally, your article reflects all the conflict that exists within you, between a brilliant past and a balanced present.

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